

Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-2',6'-Dimethylaniline Complexes with La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Gd^{3+}

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Potentiometric studies on metal complexes of La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Gd^{3+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline have been carried out. The proton-ligand dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at an ionic strength $0.1M$ (NaClO_4) in 75:25 percent (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The validity of Born's relation was examined by studying the plot of Z^2/r vs $\log K$ values of rare earth complexes of the ligand.

THE successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline with trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹ and the findings are reported in the present communication.

A precision research pH meter, Corning Model 12, with combined glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. Both the electrodes dip into the titration mixture without vitiating any results. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scales and the pH can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

Experimental

The ligand, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline was prepared and repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to get an analytically pure sample with m.p. 116° (observed).

The dioxane used was purified by the method described by Vogel². Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate, was used throughout the investigation.

The medium of titration was 75:25 per cent dioxane-water (v/v) mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion, the acid and the ligand were titrated against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide. Metal ion solutions of yttrium, gadolinium and neodymium were prepared by taking metal nitrates of A.R. grade which were converted to their respective carbonates and then to their perchlorates. Metal

ion solutions of dysprosium, praseodymium and lanthanum were prepared by taking the metal carbonates of A. R. grade which were converted to their respective perchlorates. The metal nitrates and carbonates were supplied by S. D. Lab. Chem. Industry, Bombay. All the solutions were standardised complexometrically³ by EDTA titrations. All measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.07 M) solution:

- (i) 5 ml 0.16 M HClO_4 + 5 ml 0.64 M NaClO_4 + 30 ml dioxane.
- (ii) 5 ml 0.16 M HClO_4 + 5 ml 0.64 M NaClO_4 + 60.0 mg reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane.
- (iii) 5 ml 0.64 M NaClO_4 + 5 ml metal salt 0.008 M solution in 0.16 M HClO_4 + 60.0 mg reagent to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxane.

The appropriate correction factor for converting pH meter readings (B values) to $-\log[\text{H}^+]$ in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water was applied⁴ and the curves plotted accordingly. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out values of $\bar{n}$ and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be pointed out here that the ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during titration and by the absence of any significant drift in the pH even after 1 hr. In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in complex formation and the ligand behaves as a monoprotic one.

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various pH were calculated and a curve between pH and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted (Fig. 1). The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H were evaluated by the half-integral method as well as from the plots of $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs pH and $\log (2 - \bar{n}_A) / (\bar{n}_A - 1)$ vs pH (Figs. 2 and 3). Both these values agree well.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complex ion equilibria (Fig. 4). For lanthanum and praseodymium metal systems, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated by the half-integral method. These values agree well with those obtained from

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline. Plot of $\bar{n}_A$ vs pH

Fig. 4. Metal ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline. Plot of $\bar{n}$ vs pL

Fig. 2. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline. Plot of $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs pH

Fig. 3. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline. Plot of $\log (2 - \bar{n}_A) / (\bar{n}_A - 1)$ vs pH

Fig. 5. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline. Plot of $\log \bar{n}/1-\bar{n}$ vs pL

Fig. 6. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2',6'-dimethylaniline. Plot of $\log 2-\bar{n}/\bar{n}-1$ vs pL

TABLE I—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES OF 2-HYDROXY-2',6'-DIMETHYLANILINE WITH TRIVALENT LANTHANIDES

Cations	$t=25 \pm 0.1^\circ$		$\mu=0.1$ (NaClO ₄)				
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Gd ³⁺
log K ₁	9.65	8.19	9.06	9.10	8.09	7.87	9.21
log K ₂	2.97	6.90	7.06	6.42	7.13	7.15	7.80
σ^a	± 0.025	± 0.058	± 0.058	± 0.058	± 0.07	± 0.13	± 0.038
Limits of error	± 0.018	± 0.04	± 0.03	± 0.03	± 0.04	± 0.07	± 0.03

For proton association (H⁺), K₁ corresponds to the species LH⁺, while for metal ions, K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂, respectively.

the linear plots of $\log \bar{n}/1-\bar{n}$ and $\log 2-\bar{n}/\bar{n}-1$ vs pL (Figs. 5 and 6). In the case of metal systems of neodymium, yttrium, dysprosium and gadolinium, where the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values was found to be less than 1.78 log unit, the same were calculated by the least square method. The most representative values are recorded in Table I. Standard deviations range from 0.04 to 0.13, the lower precision being observed for dysprosium. Limits of error lie between ± 0.03 and ± 0.07 . The order of stability of the trivalent metal chelates was found to be Gd > La > Pr > Y > Nd > Dy.

Rare earths normally form ionic compounds. The possibility of covalent interaction, however,

cannot be completely excluded as reported in the case of acetylacetonate chelates of rare earths⁶. If the bonds are ionic, the Born relation $E=Z^2/2r(1-1/D)$ should hold for the energy change on complexation of a gaseous ion of charge Z and radius r in a medium of dielectric constant D. Since the stability constant is related directly to this energy, the log K values should increase linearly with Z^2/r . The plots of $\log K_1$ vs Z^2/r values of the rare earth complexes do not exhibit any linear increase of $\log K_1$ with increase in Z^2/r .

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